

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STOOL ANTIGEN TEST IN THE H.PYLORI-ASSOCIATED GASTRODUODENAL PATHOLOGIES: DIAGNOSTIC OPPORTUNITIES TO DETERMINE OF THE CHARACTER AND LOCALISATION OF THE PATHOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Abstract

Determining the localization and character of the pathological process is an important issue in the diagnosis of *Helicobacter pylori* infections. The mentioned problem is currently only within the capabilities of invasive examination methods. However, the results of the research show some opportunities of using the stool antigen test, a non-invasive examination method, to differentiate of gastritis and gastroduodenal ulcer.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*, gastritis, gastric ulcer, duodenal ulcer, stool antigen test, ELISA

Helicobacter pylori is a spiral shaped bacteria that is mainly localized in the digestive tract and is present in more than half of the world's population. In 2015, approximately 4.4 billion (more than 50%) people worldwide were diagnosed with *H. pylori* infection [1]. This microorganism is not only the main causative agent of gastritis and gastric ulcer, but also a risk factor for gastric adenocarcinoma. Thus, *H. pylori* has an etiological role in approximately 50-60% of gastritis, 90% of duodenal ulcer disease, 50-80% of gastric ulcer disease, and 60-70% of gastric cancer cases [2].

There are many invasive and non-invasive examination methods for the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection. Even though all these methods are used in different frequencies, the determination of *H. pylori* in patients with gastroduodenal pathology by non-invasive methods still retains its relevance. The ideal method is one with high sensitivity and specificity, easy to apply, relatively quick response, minimally invasive, and financially inexpensive.

One of the main issues in the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infections is the determination of the localization and character of the pathological process. In other words, the location of the pathological process caused by *H. pylori* infection (in the different parts of the stomach and duodenum, etc.) and its character (gastritis, gastric and duodenal ulcer) are important for planning treatment. It is important for its implementation and satisfactory results. The above (determining the localization and nature of the pathological process) is currently only within the capabilities of invasive examination methods. Therefore, it is important to search for non-invasive examination methods to determine the localization and nature of the process or to find tests with such a possibility among the existing examination methods.

The stool antigen test is a non-invasive method used in the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection, with 94%

sensitivity and 97% specificity in a global meta-analysis. Like all methods, this method has its advantages and disadvantages. The main advantage of the test is its non-invasiveness, cost-effectiveness, routineness, accessibility, the possibility of use in any age group, etc. As mentioned above, its disadvantages are the lack of 100% sensitivity and specificity and the possibility of false positive results due to the sensitivity of the test to various adverse effects.

It is possible to quickly determine the presence of *H. pylori* antigens in the feces through the stool antigen test, which is a non-invasive examination method. A stool antigen test is also used to determine active *H. pylori* infection. Monoclonal or polyclonal antibodies are used in the preparation of these tests [3].

The results of numerous studies have confirmed the possibility of using the fecal antigen test as an alternative to invasive procedures to detect patients with *H. pylori* infection and to evaluate the effectiveness of eradication therapy [4, 5].

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the diagnostic possibilities of the stool antigen test, which is a non-invasive examination method, in gastroduodenal pathologies, as well as to evaluate its opportunities to determine the localization and nature of the pathological process.

Materials and methods. In the study, blood and stool samples taken at the same time from 110 patients with various gastroduodenal complaints (67 gastritis, 27 gastroduodenal ulcers, and 16 gastric cancer) were examined by serological method and stool antigen test. The titer of antibodies (IgM and IgG) formed against *H. pylori* in the blood serum was determined by standard enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), and *H. pylori* antigens in stool samples were determined by the express method (stool antigen test).

Statistical analysis of the results was based on parametric and non-parametric methods, and the differences between groups was determined using a p-value [6]. When evaluating the sensitivity and specificity of the research methods, the results of ELISA (presence of the *H.pylori* IgG antibodies in the blood sera of the patients) were used as a reference method ("gold standard") [7].

Results and discussion. The stool antigen test was positive in 33 (49%) and negative in 34 (51%) of 67 patients with gastritis who were positive serological testing for *H.pylori* IgG-antibodies (fig. 1). The sensitivity and specificity of the stool antigen test in the patients with gastritis were 49% and 100%, respectively.

Fig. 1. Frequency of *H.pylori* antigens in stool samples of patients with gastritis

The diagnostic capabilities of the tests applied during gastritis - the frequency of detection of *H.pylori* antibodies in the blood serum of patients by ELISA and *H.pylori* antigens in stool samples by stool antigen test are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Frequency of detection of *H.pylori* antibodies in blood serum of patients with gastritis by ELISA and *H.pylori* antigens in stool samples by stool antigen test

The stool antigen test was positive in 21 (78%) and negative in 6 (22%) of 27 patients diagnosed with *H.pylori*-associated gastric and duodenal ulcers (fig. 3). The sensitivity and specificity of this test for gastric and duodenal ulcers were 78% and 100%, respectively.

Fig. 3. Frequency of *H.pylori* antigens in stool samples of patients with gastric and duodenal ulcers

The diagnostic capabilities of the tests applied in the case of gastric and duodenal ulcers - the frequency of detection of *H.pylori* antibodies in blood serum of patients by ELISA and *H.pylori* antigens in stool samples by stool antigen test are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. The frequency of detection of *H.pylori* antibodies in blood serum of patients with gastric and duodenal ulcers by ELISA and *H.pylori* antigens in stool samples by stool antigen test

Also, 16 patients with gastric and duodenal cancer were examined in the study. *H.pylori* antigens were detected in stool samples of these patients in 10 out of 16 patients (62.5%), and the result was negative in 6 (37.5%).

The obtained results are somewhat different from the results of other studies in this field. Thus, although the stool antigen test in ulcer disease showed 73.9% sensitivity and 86.7% specificity [8], the sensitivity and specificity of serological examinations were 87.5% and 54.5%, respectively [9]. It has been shown in other studies that the express test used to determine *H.pylori* antigens in feces has low sensitivity (63.8%-71.1%),

but high specificity (91.1%-96.2%) [10]. Also, in another study conducted in the same direction, it was determined that the stool antigen test has high sensitivity and specificity (85.5%-90.8% and 91%-93.4%, respectively). In the same study, the sensitivity and specificity of ELISA were 94.7% and 97.6%, respectively [11].

Thus, as a result of research, it was determined that in the patients with *H.pylori*-associated gastric and duodenal ulcers, the stool antigen test was positive in significantly more cases than in the patients with *H.pylori*-associated gastritis (78% and 49%, respectively, $p < 0.05$). The results of the study show the perspectives of using the stool antigen test in the differentiation of gastritis and gastroduodenal ulcer diseases.

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